

Octahedral Complexes of Cobalt(II) Acetylacetonate with Aromatic Nitrogenous Bases*

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Methods of preparation of the complexes of the type $[\text{Co X}_2\text{L}_2]$ and $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})\text{L}_2]$, where LH=a molecule of acetylacetonate, X=pyridine, β -picoline, γ -picoline and AA=orthophenanthroline, and α - α' -dipyridyl have been described. Conductance values indicate non-electrolytic nature of the complexes. The complexes are all paramagnetic ($\mu = 4.9-5.2$ B.M.). Molecular weight and electronic absorption spectral data of the complexes are also reported. Octahedral structure is assigned to these complexes.

Addition of dilute ammonia to an aqueous solution of cobalt(II) chloride, acetylacetonate and pyridine results in the formation of dipyridine *bis* acetylacetonato cobalt(II). The addition of ammonia probably favours the pH for the introduction of two pyridine ligands to cobalt(II) acetylacetonate formed *in situ*. β -picoline and γ -picoline behave similarly but 2-methylpyridine is unable to form the adduct possibly due to steric influence of 2-methyl group. These complexes slowly lose the heterocyclic base when left in air for some days or on being heated and are less stable than the corresponding nickel(II) complexes¹.

The above complexes react with bidentate strongly chelating α mines such as orthophenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl providing a smooth route for the synthesis of cobalt(II) heterochelates of the type $[\text{Co}(\text{AA})\text{L}_2]$. With these chelating amines expulsion of unidentate heterocyclic base takes place at ordinary temperature. The adducts formed by these chelating ligands are quite stable and do not decompose or get oxidised even on heating at 120° for hours.

The electrolytic conductance measurements of these complexes have been completed in methanol and low molar conductance values ($\Lambda_M = 12-15$ mhos) indicate the non-electrolytic nature of the adducts.

The observed magnetic moments ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 4.9-5.2$ B.M) indicate that the structure of these cobalt(II) complexes are "high spin" octahedral (Table 1)^{2,3}.

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TABLE I

Molecular weight and Magnetic susceptibility data of Cobalt(II) Complexes

Compound	Dia. corr. $\times 10^6$	$\chi_M' \times 10^6$	$\mu_{\text{eff.}}^*$ (B.M.) T=295°K	Molecular weight	
				Found	Reqd.
[Co (Py) ₂ (acac) ₂]	-211	10,371	4.96	395	415
[Co (β -Pic) ₂ (acac) ₂]	-234	10,200	4.92	397	443
[Co (γ -Pic) ₂ (acac) ₂]	-234	10,280	4.95	400	443
[Co (ophen) (acac) ₂]	-217	11,712	5.27	462	437
[Co(dipy) (acac) ₂]	-211	11,101	5.13	494	413

where Py=pyridine; β -pic=3-methyl pyridine; γ -Pic =4-methyl pyridine; ophen=ortho-phenanthroline; dipy= α - α' -dipyridyl and acac=acetylacetonc.

*Calculated as $\mu_{\text{eff}} = 2.84 (\chi_M' \times T)^{\frac{1}{2}}$ B.M.

Octahedral cobalt(II) compounds should have three spin allowed d-d transitions and exhibit three absorption bands^{2,4-5} around 8,400, 18,000 and 20,000 cm^{-1} due to the transitions $4T_{2g} \leftarrow 4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_1), $4A_{2g} \leftarrow 4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_2) and $4T_{1g}$ (P) $\leftarrow 4T_{1g}$ (F) (ν_3) respectively. On the other hand tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes¹⁶ should show bands in a lower frequency region (the highest frequency band being in the region around 15,000 cm^{-1}) associated with the transition, $4T_{1g}$ (P) $\leftarrow 4A_{2g}$ with $\epsilon \sim 10^2$ as compared to $\epsilon \sim 10$ for octahedral complexes⁶⁻⁹). The electronic spectra of these complexes in ethanol were recorded in the region of 28,570-10,000 cm^{-1} . One main band around 22,220 cm^{-1} and two shoulders around 20,000 and 18,500 cm^{-1} have been observed in case of pyridine, β -picoline and γ -picoline complexes (cf Table II). As the band in the near infra red region corresponds to the ν_1 transition, the observed bands should be assigned among ν_2 and ν_3 transitions, one having probably double peak. This double peak may be expected only in case of $4T_{1g}$ (P) $\leftarrow 4T_{1g}$ (F) transition due to the spin-orbit splitting of the $4T_{1g}$ (P) state. Furthermore, it has been frequently observed in octahedral cobalt(II) complexes that the ν_3 band involving one electron transition is stronger than ν_2 band involving two electron transition¹⁴. The configurations of the levels T_{1g} (F), T_{1g} (P) and A_{2g} are $t_{2g}^5 e_g^2$, $t_{2g}^4 e_g^3$ and $t_{2g}^3 e_g^4$ respectively. It is therefore plausible to assign the intense bands around 22,220 and 20,000 cm^{-1} as the ν_3 transition and the band around 18,500 cm^{-1} as the ν_2 transition. In case of cobalt (II) heterochelates containing ortho-phenanthroline and α - α' -dipyridyl none of these bands was observed in the region studied.

A *cis* configuration is assigned to the complexes of the type [Co X₂L₂] based on the chemical evidences. The dipyrindine (di- β -picoline/di- γ -picoline) complex react with bidentate chelating ligands such as ortho-phenanthroline or α - α' -dipyridyl at ordinary temperature with the instantaneous expulsion of pyridine (β -picoline/ γ -picoline) and formation of cobalt(II) heterochelates. If these complexes would belong to the *trans* configuration,

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expulsion of monodentate amines should have taken place at a higher temperature in order to initiate *trans-cis* isomerisation. This type of chemical evidence along with others has been utilised recently in our Laboratory to characterise geometrical isomers of few cobaltic complexes.¹⁰ Although conductance, electronic spectra have been claimed to distinguish geometrical isomers of cobaltic complexes of the type $[\text{Co}^{\text{III}}\text{A}_4\text{B}_2]^{2+}$, these studies are of little help in characterising *cis-trans* isomers of cobaltous complexes of the type $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{A}_4\text{B}_2]$.

Molecular weight of these complexes were determined in benzene as outlined previously and results are in close agreement with the calculated value (Table I). Thermal dissociation studies of these complexes are in progress and will be reported in a later communication.

TABLE II

Analysis, Colour, Molar conductance and Electronic absorption spectral data of Cobalt(II) Complexes

Complex	Analysis		Colour	Molar conductance mhos $\text{cm}^2 \text{mole}^{-1}$	Wave number ν , cm^{-1}	Molar absorptivity litre $\text{mole}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$
	Found %	Reqd. %				
[Co(Py) ₂ (acac) ₂]	Co, 14.0	14.2	Dull-red needles	12	22,220-	28 ^a
	N, 6.9	6.7			21,740	25
					20,410-sh 20,000	20
[Co(β -Pic) ₂ (acac) ₂]	Co, 13.5	13.3	Dull-red needles	12	22,220-	30 ^b
	N, 6.1	6.3			21,680	25
					18,520-sh 18,180	20
[Co(γ -Pic) ₂ (acac) ₂]	Co, 13.1	13.3	Dull-red needles	14	22,220-	28 ^c
	N, 6.2	6.3			21,740	25
					18,520-sh 18,180	21
[Co(ophen)(acac) ₂]	Co, 13.2	13.4	Orange-yellow	15	—	—
[Co(dipy)(acac) ₂]	Co, 14.0	14.2	Orange	15	—	—
	N, 6.9	6.7				

'a' means ethanol solution and small amount of pyridine.

'b' means ethanol solution and small amount of β -picoline.

'c' means ethanol solution and small amount of γ -picoline.

sh=shoulder.

Abbreviations as under Table I.

EXPERIMENTAL

Methods : Conductance measurements were performed in methanol at 30° with the help of a Philip's Conductivity Bridge and a dip type cell. Absorption spectra was recorded in a Hilger Watts Uvispeck Spectrophotometer using one cm. cells. Magnetic susceptibility was determined by a Gouy Balance using G.R. copper sulphate pentahydrate as the standard and using a field strength of about 8.0×10^3 gauss. Diamagnetic correction of the ligands was applied by the use of Pascal's constants¹¹.

Preparation of Cobalt(II) complexes :

METHOD 1. *For complexes of the type (Co X₂L₂).* Cobalt(II) chloride hexahydrate (0.47 g) was dissolved in water (10 ml.) and added to a mixture of acetylacetone (0.40 g) and the requisite heterocyclic base (1 ml.) The pH of the mixture was adjusted to 4 by addition of dilute ammonium hydroxide dropwise with stirring. The separated dull-red precipitates were filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol containing a small amount of the heterocyclic base. The complexes were dried in air.

Method 2 *For Complexes of the type [Co(AA)L₂].* Dipyridine bis acetylacetone cobalt(II) (0.004 moles) as prepared above was dissolved in minimum amount of ethanol. Ortho-phenanthroline/ α - α' -dipyridyl (0.004 moles) was dissolved in ethanol (5ml.) These two solutions were then mixed and allowed to stand for an hour with occasional stirring. The separated orange crystals were filtered off and recrystallised from ethanol and dried in air.

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